

Flipped Classroom for the Untaught Least Learned Competencies in Mathematics

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative research aimed to determine the Flipped Classroom benefits to seventh-grade learners and mathematics teachers in resolving the untaught least learned competencies by the end of the school year. The flipped classroom with the researcher-made flipped videos was utilized as an intervention to compare it to the prevailing teaching approach. This method enables learners to study independently without the anxiety that comes with the prevailing math instruction. The study utilized a quasi-experimental research design since the two research groups were purposefully chosen from a diverse learner population. The research used a control group exposed to the prevailing teaching method and an experimental group exposed to the flipped classroom approach. A 50-item multiple-choice questionnaire validated by a panel of experts was utilized to determine changes before and after the intervention. The study's results indicated that learners' test scores increased dramatically after the interventions performed in the prevailing and flipped classroom approaches. However, the outcome of learners subjected to the prevailing method and those exposed to the flipped classroom approach was comparable. Although the results showed that no group substantially differed from the other, for the optimistic viewpoint, it is conclusive to declare that flipped classrooms may enhance learner performance in the same manner that the prevailing teaching method does. Furthermore, the flipped classroom could foster learners' interest while augmenting the teacher's absence in school. Hence, the flipped classroom can be an alternative way to teach mathematics and a strong recommendation for teachers with uncertain responsibilities due to ancillary school functions.

Keywords:

flipped classroom, ancillary functions, quasi-experimental research design, untaught least learned competencies, Central Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are the facilitators of learning, and the learner's success is determined mainly by the quality of the teacher (Sharma, 2019). That is why teachers play an important part in providing an engaging learning environment, like flipping the discussions where learners may achieve academically based on their interests and what would fit them most (Rashid & Zaman, 2018). However, some factors affecting teachers' performance in their duties also affect their learners' performances (Siachifuwe, 2017). Like what Into, & Gempes (2018) said, most school teachers claimed that factors such as heavy workloads and ancillary services in school

hindered quality education in the country. Moreover, according to Saloviita and Pakarinen (2021), multiple ancillary functions among school teachers often lead to a loss of motivation, satisfaction, and competence, as well as feelings of burnout. Yarkwan and Agyei (2018) also contend that school events, such as a prolonged celebration of a sports festival, have no beneficial effects on learners' academic performance. Likewise, school closures due to weather and natural catastrophes, absenteeism, and any other reason for being absent (Kuhfeld et al., 2020), and holidays associated with locally celebrated festivals (Gonzales, 2017) have a detrimental impact on students' learning. These are some of the reasons that affect teachers' performance in school,

and some consider them accountable for lengthy school activities comparable to sports. According to Bradley (2016), extracurricular activities may seem to be advantageous at first since students may engage more thoroughly in sports, community outreach, and even apprenticeships. Unfortunately, this brings us back to the initial issue of a persistent lack of understanding among learners due to the adverse effects on lecture time. As a result, due to reduced contact hours for learners and a lack of interaction with teachers when experiencing problems in learning/understanding, the quality of academic performances of learners are declining in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics or STEM (Sintema, 2020).

In the Philippines, despite all the factors affecting teacher's performances in school, such as school activities, typhoons, flooding, other weather disturbances, calamities, local holidays due to festivals, and teacher ancillary functions in school, the teachers are still required to have make-up classes for the lost schooldays (DepEd Order 009, 2005; DepEd Order 109, 2009). These Orders encourage classroom teachers to reschedule the lost school days outside of the school calendar, particularly on Saturdays, mid-year break, or the remaining months of the school year. Therefore, the school, particularly the subject teachers, could undertake any form of modularized instruction that would allow learners to complete studies at home to compensate for the loss of class hours. Hence, the development of any form of instructional materials is a tool for the effective academic performance of learners (DepEd Order 35, s. 1998). Similarly, the DepEd Learning Action Cell (LAC) agreed that researching solutions to meet the stated need may take the shape of learning materials, instructional materials, equipment, facilities, teaching methods, teaching mode, and so on (DepEd Order 35, s. 2016). However, despite all these DepEd Orders, some teachers in any discipline, especially mathematics teachers, continue to be blind and deaf, leaving some learning competencies unattained in the last quarter of the curriculum guide before the school year ends (Orale & Uy, 2018). These are the situations of public school teachers who are still blind and deaf in attending missed learning competencies every school year because they are preoccupied with their responsibilities as teachers and parents at home.

Consequently, since the expected benefits of the spiral progression approach in the Philippine DepEd's K to 12 Basic Education Program (DepEd Order 31, 2012) were not realized, all subjects, like Mathematics, shifted to a broken spiral (Orale & Uy, 2018). Thus, the factors influencing teachers' performance to be low-performing

teachers in their duties also affect their learners' performance to be low-performing learners (Haramain, 2019). Nevertheless, the teacher has a critical part in creating an inspiring learning environment for their learners to succeed academically (Rashid & Zaman, 2018). That is why teachers must constantly develop their instructional methods by studying internet media and modern informatory resources to add creativity to their classrooms (Akram, 2010).

Because of the aforementioned factors affecting teachers' responsibilities, which also involve learners' performances as cited in an international educational setting (Siachifuwe, 2017) and the Philippine educational setting (Haramain, 2019), the researcher found it challenging to ultimately cope with the DepEd's Curriculum Guide (2016). Therefore, the researcher initially sought to examine and identify solutions to the observed gaps in his classroom setting utilizing this quasi-experimental action research design in his study. Furthermore, the researcher became involved in addressing this issue of the untaught least learned competencies in Mathematics 7, which happened in the last quarter of the curriculum guide in the content of Statistics and Probability. Statistics and Probability is one of the contents in the mathematics curriculum guide in grades 7 to 10 (DepEd Mathematics Curriculum Guide, 2016). In fact, according to the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) and Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) International Study Center, countries just like the United States of America, Canada, Hongkong, Spain, Philippines, among others, have this mathematical content of statistics and probability in the last quarter of their curriculum guide (Mullis et al., 2016). Since this content's Statistics and Probability fall in the last quarter of the school year, the researcher discovered that it always has a low degree of competence in higher grades. This allegation was confirmed by (da Silva et al., 2020) that mathematics teachers often overlooked this topic statistics and probability due to various reasons comparable to teachers' ancillary functions in school. Thus, these unattained learning competencies became the least learned competencies in the higher grades, particularly in grade 10 mathematics, under the content of statistics and probability (Ferrer, 2017). In addition, the identified least-learned skills during the DepEd Regional Mass Training on K to 12 for Grade-7 teachers covered seven (7) out of the twelve (12) learning competencies in the last quarter Mathematics 7 curriculum guide (Temelo & Sillorequez, 2013). As a result, the researcher got interested in employing Information and Communications Technology

(ICT) to appeal to digital native learners using the Flipped Classroom teaching approach to his instructions. ICT in mathematics education benefits both the teaching and learning processes (Das, 2019). Thus, the ICT supports mathematics teachers in developing their instructional preparation, teaching-learning strategies, keeping up to date on subjective and pedagogical knowledge, and enhancing a range of other related skills. It is also helpful to students since it motivates and engages them in their studies, builds confidence in their mathematical abilities, and allows them to express and produce various subjective and objective thoughts (Joshi, 2017).

The flipped classroom method utilizing the researcher-made *flipped videos* was the intervention for the study. This intervention was used to resolve the existing problems surrounding the untaught least learned competencies comprising the least-learned skills of learners in the last quarter of the mathematical content - statistics and probability (Temelo & Sillorequez, 2013). This intervention of having flipped videos for instruction was based on the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning, which states that “it is a constructivist approach to learning, in which multimedia are seen as cognitive tools for knowledge creation rather than information delivery methods” (Mayer, 2014). Likewise, according to Gutierrez (2014), there were three (3) key concepts that will help educators to understand student’s learning in the digital age through these three methodologies: *Heutagogy* (Hase & Kenyon, 2000), encourages learners to become more self-directed, *Peeragogy* (Rheingold et al., 2015), focuses in co-learning and co-creating, and *Cybergogy* (Wang & Kang, 2006), promotes learner engagement in an online environment.

A flipped classroom is a teaching approach that reverses imparted information and knowledge internalization compared to a prevailing classroom (Garza, 2014). The conventional roles of teachers and learners may change in this classroom environment, and the class schedule may be altered (Coronacion & Roman, 2019). Thus, learning activity creates a novel learning experience for learners by constructing an individual and cooperative learning environment. According to Szparagowski (2014), the flipped classroom is some kind of education in which learners encounter fresh features outside of class rather than conventional review exercises. Also, the term “flipped classroom” refers to a pedagogical method in which instructions from the classroom learning environment to the individual learning space became a dynamic and immersive learning environment where the teacher guides learners as they implement concepts and communicate creatively in the subject matter (Flipped

Learning Network, 2014). ‘The flipped classroom is an example of pedagogy associated with twenty-first-century learners’ teaching and learning processes’ (Avery & Huggan, 2018). Similarly, flipped classroom models can be a potentially helpful way for teachers to encourage more engaging approaches to K-12 Math teaching and learning, such as problem-based or project-based approaches (Katsa et al., 2016). Likewise, the flipped classroom was associated with significant increases in learners’ mathematical learning performance, and it was particularly beneficial to learners in the middle stages of mathematics (Wei et al., 2020). Hence, the researcher believes that flipped classrooms are an innovative solution to preparing learners for the 21st-century workforce. It fosters technology, media, knowledge, teamwork, engagement, analytical thought, and innovation.

Consequently, the purpose of this study was to see how the Flipped Classrooms method, which used researcher-made flipped videos, affected learners’ performance in the most neglected and least learned learning competencies in Mathematics 7 throughout the school year. Furthermore, utilizing the quasi-experimental research design helped teachers attain the DepEd’s curriculum guide’s prescribed learning competencies without interfering with their roles and obligations as teachers or with ancillary functions in school. Thus, this experimental research study specifically sought to address the following research questions: (1) What is the learner’s performance in the pre-test among those used to the prevailing approach and the flipped classroom? (2) Is there a significant difference in pre-test results between those used to the prevailing method and those exposed to the flipped classroom? (3) What is the learner’s post-test performance among those subjected to the prevailing approach and the flipped classroom? (4) Is there a significant difference in post-test results between those subject to the prevailing method and those exposed to the flipped classroom? (5) What actions should be taken to incorporate the Flipped Classroom approach into mathematics instruction to address the untaught least learned competencies in mathematics 7?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The researcher employed the quasi-experimental research design (White & Sabarwal, 2014). As seen Figure 1, it illustrates the study’s conceptual structure. Two classes of the sample population were subjected to two different teaching approaches: the experimental group utilizing the flipped classroom and the control group using the prevailing teaching method. The same testing instruments were utilized in the pre-test and post-

test before and after the conducted interventions (Yusuf et al., 2017).

The study utilized descriptive and inferential analyses (Chanoknath & Louangrath, 2015) to evaluate Flipped

Classroom's results as an alternative method in teaching mathematics in resolving current issues of skipped and untaught learning competencies, especially in the last quarter of Mathematics 7 content.

Figure 1. The quasi-experimental research design's conceptual framework.

Participants and other Sources of Data and Information

The researcher selected two (2) out of the seven (7) sections from a heterogeneous group of learners. These two (2) of the classes were purposefully chosen, which happened to be the last two sections in Grade 7; Grade 7 - Caticlan & Grade 7 - Dumlog of Malay National High Schools for the school year 2017 – 2018. There were 28 males, 22 females for a total of 50 learners in Grade 7-Caticlan, and there were 29 males, 21 females for a total of 50 learners in Grade 7-Dumlog; an overall of 100 learners as the total population. The chosen two groups of respondents were the only classes handled by the researcher in grade 7 and the only convenient schedule to conduct research. One sample group underwent the prevailing teaching type under the control group through a quasi-experimental research design. In contrast, the other sample group experienced the flipped classroom approach in the experimental group's teaching. The seven (7) weeks duration sustained the entire study as stated in the fourth quarter learning competency codes in Math 7 under (DepEd's K to 12 Mathematics Curriculum Guide, August 2016).

Data Gathering Methods

First, the research instrument was developed based on pilot testing (Fraser et al., 2018) and item analysis (Smriti, 2018) before and after its utilization. This questionnaire consisted of 50 multiple-choice questions anchored to the learning competencies under fourth-quarter mathematics 7 in the DepEd Curriculum Guide (2016). Next, the created research instrument was subject to validation; that is why the researcher asked a mathematics expert panel of evaluators to assess the construct's content feasibility. The

researcher then applied the final testing instrument to both groups: the control group, which used the prevailing teaching approach, and the experimental group, which used the flipped classroom teaching method. Finally, the data was collected and processed for statistical analysis by comparing pre-test scores to all respondents' post-test scores. When the results came out, the researcher held a focus group discussion (FGD) with his fellow mathematics teachers at school and the principal. The FGD was led by these open-ended questions and informal interviews to determine how flipped classrooms might be implemented in school, particularly for teachers who are often away due to school-related functions.

The study was a quantitative type of research that measured the numbers derived from the empirical findings and data collection. In this study, the researcher used a 5% standard of meaning to decide whether to consider or deny the null hypothesis. For descriptive analysis, the mean and standard deviation were utilized (Rocha & Mondelli, 2020). Since these two respondents were purposefully chosen, the Mann-Whitney-U Test was employed in the two independent sample means for the inferential analysis (Nachar, 2008). To generate significant differences, the researcher utilized the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software (Allahawiah & Al Saraireh, 2014).

Intervention

The researcher's intervention was called the Flipped Classroom method using the researcher-made flipped video in teaching. The converted offline videos are the educational equivalent of the flipped classroom used for instruction. These researcher-made videos in his

intervention helped learners learn materials' content while not in the classroom's four corners. Usually, the 15-minute video contains the following lectures anchored from the DepEd Curriculum Guide (2016), activities, quizzes, and some assignments. Flipped videos included vlogs or video blogging, which were more entertaining to learners. Videos are created from converting PowerPoint presentations accompanied by voice recordings and visual pictures into moving visuals for teaching. Furthermore, the researcher used Filmora, Audacity, Photoshop Adobe, and Open Broadcaster Software (OBS) as practical applications in making flipped videos. After the completed study, the school and district Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRDMS) coordinators evaluated and checked these videos to consistently use resources at the school and district levels. Likewise, the researcher could keep these videos for future use of his instructions.

Study's Interventions Procedure

Teaching methods refer to the procedures utilized by the teacher in his classroom to organize instructions and execute the curriculum. These are techniques and strategies used based on educational theories that forecast behaviors under certain pedagogical conditions (Abah, 2020). According to Ullah and Iqbal (2020), teachers in today's classrooms use two different types of teaching methods: (1) the traditional (conventional) method of teaching, which is the prevailing lecture type of teaching that focuses on memorization and recitation, and (2) the modern teaching methodology that focuses on interactive activities. This interactive teaching methodology is now associated with educational technology (Tuma, 2021), which is commonly used as an intervention in modern days through distance, online, and blended learning (Rosenbusch, 2020). These are teaching platforms that are widely used in this pandemic-related health crisis (Al-Marroof et al., 2020).

The researcher utilized the quasi-experimental research design with two independent sample groups, the control group, and the experimental group, in this study. The researcher employed the *Prevailing Method* of teaching in the control group utilizing the typical lecture type of instruction socially (face-to-face) using the chalk and chalkboard, paper and pen, manila paper, recitation, memorization, drills or quizzes, seatwork, group activities, and so on. Furthermore, the researcher utilized the textbook provided by DepEd as the primary source of instruction to support the teaching and learning in the mathematics curriculum. Since the textbooks are limited in the Philippines public high schools (Read & Atinc,

2017; Hernando-Malipot, 2019), learners underwent reading and copying what is on the textbook when the teacher is unavailable due to unexpected circumstances school's additional functions. Consequently, the latter statement was experienced several times even during experimentation because the researcher was assigned to various school functions such as mathematics coordinator, ICT coordinator, LIS (Learners Information System) & EBEIS (Enhanced Basic Education Information System) coordinator, aside from being a classroom subject teacher. Therefore, this group was given some seatwork or tasks at home without teacher intervention. Furthermore, when the teacher returns to school, this group will continue to have classes to deal with their assigned tasks such as homework, group projects, group work activities, etc.

On the other hand, the experimental group used the *Flipped Classroom* approach of teaching with the help of researcher-created videos. These are the pre-recorded video lectures produced by the researcher to cover the possibility that he may be unavailable from class discussions due to unexpected reasons. The implementation of this intervention usually occurred in distance education (Sumuglu, 2021), where the teacher and learners are physically separated during class discussions in continuing education (Cassiba et al., 2021). Fidalgo et al. (2020) supported this assertion by stating that distance education is an educational experience in which teachers and learners are separated in time and space. The flipped classroom is a technology-based approach that was anticipated to be done outside the four corners of the classroom. However, Lo and Hew (2017) said that flipped classroom is a method that learners could learn inside and outside the classroom. The only difference was that learners might have less time to review the flipped videos inside the school than outside of the school when learners review them at home. Thus, in this study, when the teacher is at school doing ancillary functions and cannot attend his class, these flipped videos are used as an instructional support method for the whole class period. Learners often viewed these videos in their classroom through multimedia presentations or e-classroom (computer room) to avoid missing lectures. Furthermore, when the teacher is out for a long period of time due to training or seminars attended and other unforeseen circumstances, flipped videos are posted to any social media platform so that learners may access them online. The uploaded flipped videos are accompanied by lectures and certain activities to be completed before returning to school. Teachers may then ensure that learners have not missed any competencies in

the curriculum guide and would be able to continue the lessons. Moreover, if learners cannot access or view the uploaded flipped videos online, they may watch them in school with the help of the school ICT teacher assigned to the e-classroom. Then, they were given ample time to finish their performance tasks for consideration.

Ethical Issues

The respondents' involvement was critical to the study's success. Thus, strict adherence to ethical principles is essential to prevent conflicts with research participants in the course of this study. By writing a formal letter detailing the intent, benefactors, timetable, scheme, and target respondents concerned, the researcher sought permission from the principal to conduct his school's experimental research. Likewise, parental consent was sought, confirming that their children were selected to participate in the study. The study's ultimate goal started if parents agreed to the researcher's conditions by affixing their signatures on the parental consent. These particular conditions involve presenting the research results in public and publishing research results in any national or international reputable journal. The orientations, instructions, and development of the study are all eagerly awaited the whole time. The documents and results obtained from respondents were completely private and solely utilized for research purposes (Yilmaz et al., 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pretest Performance in the Fourth Quarter Learning Competencies

The learner's performance in the pre-test relative to those exposed in the control group or Prevailing Method ($M=5.52, SD=2.02$) and the experimental group or Flipped Classroom ($M=6.08, SD=1.65$) deemed to be "Not Acceptable" since the mean scores were too low, falling below half of the mean scores. Descriptions of the reflected scales with the corresponding verbal interpretations are shown below in Table 1. Prior to the intervention, both groups showed comparable levels of learner performance, according to these results.

Difference in the Pre-test of Prevailing and Flipped Classroom in the Fourth Quarter Mathematics 7 Learning Competencies

Utilizing the Mann-Whitney-U test to determine learners' performance in the pre-test scores between the control group (Prevailing Method) and experimental group (Flipped classroom) as seen in Table 2.

Table 1. Learners' Performance in the Pre-Test Exposed for the Prevailing Method and Flipped Classroom.

Group	n	Mean	SD	Description
Prevailing Method	50	5.52	2.02	Not acceptable
Flipped Classroom	50	6.08	1.65	Not acceptable

Note: Description that corresponds with the following scale. 35.00 – 50.00 (Highly Acceptable), 18.00 – 34.00 (Acceptable), 1.00 – 17.00 (Not Acceptable).

The findings revealed that there was no statistically meaningful gap in the pre-test scores of learners exposed in $U(N_{prevailing}=50, N_{flipped}=50) = 979.50, z = -1.90, p = 0.06$. This result explains a comparable level of thinking to both groups in mathematics seven fourth-quarter learning competencies before the interventions. These results also indicate the homogeneity of the test scores for both groups in pre-test is similar. Thus, their understanding levels were alike towards the fourth quarter learning competencies in Mathematics 7 with no prior knowledge of the experimentation process topics. Though they were selected purposely as respondents, results showed that they came from a homogeneous group of learners with seven performances of the same mathematics level.

Table 2. Difference in the Pre-Test Exposed for the Prevailing Method and Flipped Classroom

Test	Group	N	U	z	p-value
Pre-Test	Prevailing Method	50	979.50	-1.90	0.06
	Flipped Classroom	50			

Post-test Performance in the Fourth Quarter Learning Competencies

The learner's performance in the post-test to those exposed in the control group or Prevailing Method ($M=25.78, SD=9.39$) and experimental group or Flipped Classroom ($M=30.08, SD=9.71$) deemed to be "Acceptable" because the mean scores of both groups exceeded half of the scores as shown in Table 3. Although the results showed that both groups' mean scores did not meet the 75% required to have a mastery level of all the learning competencies in the fourth quarter, it still signifies a drastic increase of the scores compared to the pre-test scores. As a consequence of the intervention, the findings showed that both groups performed well.

Table 3. Learners' Performance in the Post-Test Exposed for the Prevailing Method and Flipped Classroom.

Group	n	Mean	SD	Description
Prevailing Method	50	25.78	9.39	Acceptable
Flipped Classroom	50	30.08	9.71	Acceptable

Note: Description that corresponds with the following scale. 35.00 – 50.00 (Highly Acceptable), 18.00 – 34.00 (Acceptable), 1.00 – 17.00 (Not Acceptable).

Difference in the Post-test Performance of Prevailing and Flipped Classroom in the Fourth Quarter Mathematics 7 Learning Competencies

Utilizing the Mann-Whitney-U test to determine learners' performance in the post-test scores between the control group (Prevailing Method) and experimental group (Flipped classroom) as seen in Table 4. The findings revealed that there was no statistically meaningful gap in the post-test scores of learners exposed in $U (N_{prevailing}= 50, N_{flipped} = 50) = 976.50, z = -1.89, p = 0.06$. The comparable findings illustrate that no group performed much higher than the other, considering that one of the classes experienced interventions, the Flipped Classroom, in the experimental group. As a result, in a positive perspective, "flipped classroom" may also be seen as an alternative teaching method in some unpredictable situations affecting teacher absences and other ancillary functions provided by teachers in school. In this manner, teachers could begin their lessons using the "flipped classroom" method. Likewise, they might use the flipped classroom method to reduce untaught least learned competencies, especially in mathematics seven fourth quarter. Therefore, the researcher concluded that flipped classroom is analogous to prevailing teaching approaches in that it would boost learners' success even though a teacher does not monitor them.

Table 4. Difference in the Post-Test Exposed for the Prevailing Method and Flipped Classroom

Test	Group	N	U	z	p-value
Post-Test	Prevailing Method	50	976.50	-1.89	0.06
	Flipped Classroom	50			

Actions Taken in Integrating Flipped Classroom in Teaching Mathematics 7 Untaught Least Learned Competencies

These actions could be made possible but are not limited to reporting the study's significant findings to school administrators to gain stakeholder support for widespread implementation of this flipped classroom in schools (Abulencia, 2019). However, the same is true for reporting to higher-level authorities, such as district supervisors and education program supervisors in Mathematics, in order to assist teachers' ongoing professional development based on DepEd's commitment and the principle of life-long learning via Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions (DepEd Order 35, 2016). Thus, the researcher could develop programs to disseminate how this flipped classroom might be helpful for classroom teachers with ancillary functions in school through this school-based Learning Action Cell (LAC) and In-service Training (INSET) for public school teachers in the district or division level. Similarly, the researcher may share how to create flipped videos using the available applications on the internet for long-term educational sustainability development. Finally, since this experimental research was employed to take action on the identified issues surrounding teaching and learning mathematics 7, the researcher had to put this intervention flipped classroom into practice. Likewise, some teachers may apply this intervention in any discipline at higher grade levels. Moreover, to attain the required learning competencies for learners before the school year ends, this flipped classroom may be utilized in any quarter to eliminate the untaught least learned competencies prerequisite to the higher grade learning competencies. This platform could help teachers manage their time and practice equally to learners who were still studying independently with this method even without teacher supervision.

CONCLUSION

The flipped classroom approach, which made use of researcher-created videos, was used not just to help learners progress in the most neglected learning competencies in mathematics, especially in the last quarter of the curriculum guide. But, it was also designed for teachers to reduce the untaught learning competencies before the end of the school year due mainly to various circumstances affecting their responsibilities comparable to ancillary functions in school. Though, it is clear that student academic performance was influenced by teacher performance in school. However, despite all the clamor of public school teachers regarding the excessive paperworks and systems implemented in a top-down

approach, the Department of Education (DepEd) maintained that all of its requirements were lawful and essential for the development of basic education. Just like what the (DepEd Order 009, 2005; DepEd Order 109, 2009); with any factors resulting in loss of school days, the teachers should take make-up classes, particularly on Saturdays, mid-year break, or the remaining months of the school year. Thus, public school teachers could design any form of modularized instruction that would allow learners to complete their learnings at home to compensate for the loss of class hours (DepEd Order 35, 1998), and it was supported by the DepEd Learning Action Cell (LAC), that exploring interventions to address the identified need could be in the form of learning materials, instructional materials, equipment, facilities, teaching strategies, teaching modality, and so on (DepEd Order 35, 2016). As a result, this Flipped Classroom was developed as an intervention in the researcher's identified gaps in his classroom.

Flipped classrooms develop learners to learn more deeply where they became responsible in accomplishing their work, creates meaningful engagement with their teacher and classmates, and enhances their understanding of the materials, especially in mathematics. Through this method (flipped classroom), learners could learn the most neglected learning competencies in the last quarter of the curriculum guide, even if the teachers are not physically present in the classroom. Consequently, learners could grasp prerequisite concepts at the lower grade level before progressing to more complex concepts in the higher grade level. Hence, the goal of the DepEd's K to 12 spiral progressions has been fulfilled since no more untaught learning competencies would be neglected through this flipped classroom approach in teaching.

Furthermore, the flipped classroom could also be beneficial for teachers to continue their functions in school without affecting their duties as classroom teachers. They could maximize their time and effort by doing some instructional materials for their learners, where they can still use the flipped videos for future use. Similarly, the possibilities to achieve all of the learning competencies in the curriculum guide have been met through this flipped classroom to capacitate learners of the prerequisite concepts when they reach the higher grades.

Significant Findings

The study's significant findings are as follows. First, learners' performance levels in the pre-test exposed to different treatments were deficient before the intervention. Since the mean scores do not surpass half of

the scores displayed in the description, the verbal interpretation observed was "Not Acceptable" in their pretest scores. Second, their performance levels were similar, with no noticeable variation in pre-test ratings between the two groups with different treatments. The results revealed that their performance levels in terms of mathematical content in grade seven are comparable. Likewise, both groups showed no previous awareness of mathematics seven topics in the fourth-quarter academic competencies, though they were selected purposively by the researcher. As a result, the researcher supported the null statement and was able to carry out the research. Third, the learner's performance level in the post-test in both groups exposed for prevailing methods and flipped classrooms moved towards mastery level. Their post-test scores increased intensively as compared to their pre-test scores. As a result, the researcher decided "Acceptable" for both groups' mean scores after the experiment since their scores surpassed half of the test scores described in the definition. Finally, there was no statistically significant change in post-test results between the two treatment groups (Somerville, 2013). However, the results revealed that learners subjected to the Flipped Classroom and Prevailing Method of teaching saw substantial improvements in post-test scores compared to pre-test scores. Though comparable findings illustrate that no group performed much higher than the other, considering that one of the classes experienced interventions, the Flipped Classroom, in the experimental group. However, the flipped classroom will still serve as an alternative intervention from the optimistic viewpoint as the prevailing teaching method does. As a result, the researcher concluded that "Flipped Classroom," like the prevailing approach to teaching, would improve learners' success even if no teacher is supervising the learners and even outside of the typical classroom setting.

Implications

After the completion of this research project, the researcher discovered that the study's findings had some implications for both theory and practice.

For the theory, the study's significant findings that flipped classrooms were similar to prevailing teaching methods affirmed that this could be applied as a mastery learning model that requires each learner to master a subject before going on to the next level (Ramakrishnan & Priya, 2016). Furthermore, the implementation of this spiral development, especially in mathematics, maybe improved through different instructional procedures comparable to flipped classrooms (Perez et al., 2020). Moreover, Fernandez-Martin et al. (2020) claim that the

adoption of Flipped Classroom improved learners' understanding and attitudes toward mathematical content and discipline. Additionally, elements such as collaborative work, autonomy, self-regulation in learning, and academic performance benefitted from this method.

For the learner's practice. This flipped classroom revealed that the effectiveness was comparable to the prevailing teaching method. However, it was deemed helpful to learners to learn the most neglected learning competencies in the last quarter of the curriculum guide. Learners will gain confidence due to being equipped with fundamental ideas when they go to a higher level. As a result, anxiety about studying mathematics changed from having a good attitude towards it, resulting from the spiral progression approach in teaching (Kunwar, 2020). Likewise, learners highly accepted the researcher-made flipped videos since the language used, intonation, and accent is familiar to them compared to the foreign recorded instructional videos taken from any social media platform (Ulker et al., 2021). Hence, the researcher believes that flipped classrooms are an innovative solution to preparing digital native learners for the 21st-century workforce. It fosters technology, media, knowledge, teamwork, engagement, analytical thought, and innovation.

For the teacher's practice. This flipped classrooms are beneficial to teachers for the following reasons: (1) save time by developing essential support instructional materials once preserved, shared, and disseminated to a variety of course or social media platforms for future use, (2) teachers may constantly improve the limits of their flipped videos, allowing them to identify the instructional video's shortcomings when utilized repeatedly, (3) guarantee that their own missed lessons due to ancillary functions in school do not constitute a loss of learning for learners, particularly the essential learning competencies as they progress to higher grade levels, (4) capable of performing both roles as a regular classroom teaching adviser and a teacher with ancillary functions in school without compromising obligations in achieving sustainable development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The flipped classroom is an educational approach that requires time and effort on the teacher's part in preparing, recording, and editing a high-quality video presentation to be presented to learners through various teaching modalities. The most well-known scheme by which learners can effectively access this intervention is through social networking sites such as YouTube, Facebook, and the like. Learners could, however, view these filmed

videos (flipped classroom) in their respective classrooms or via the school's audio-visual room, e-classroom, or even in their separate audio-visual room throughout the class hour. This solution might include an opportunity for a teacher to fill in for him for a short period due to ancillary functions at school such as meetings, seminars, reports, evaluation, and the like. Others could be in the context of an online forum where there are unforeseeable disasters that prohibit learners from attending classes.

Moreover, the purpose of this study was to promote the researcher's advocacy for his whole duration of service, which is "to diminish the untaught least learned competencies in teaching Mathematics." Similarly, as the District Mathematics Coordinator for Secondary Schools, he is accountable for inspiring and motivating those to continue what he has begun. The top research priorities are to share the results at his present school, the Malay National High School in Motag, Malay, Aklan, and his school's district, the Malay District in Aklan. Thus, attaining the goal to finish all the learning competencies of the DepEd's K to 12 Curriculum Guide of 2016 may resolve through this Flipped Classroom approach in teaching due to some teacher's factors affecting their duties. Hence, it is conclusive that Mathematics teachers in Grade 7 should use flipped classrooms in their teaching and learning process. Other grade-level teachers teaching in other disciplines should also apply recorded videos to support instructional materials covering and coping with the fourth quarter's learning competencies by the end of the school year.

Finally, the researcher emanated that he should continue doing research that significantly contributes to his work. Hence, this intervention was an avenue for the learners' academic improvement, especially for teachers in their professional and personal purposes. Likewise, the study's result will be presented to his immediate supervisor regarding the study's remarkable outcome to improve learner's performance in the most neglected learning competencies in the fourth quarter. As a Mathematics coordinator in school and the district, the researcher will conduct focus group discussion (FGD) among Grade 7 Mathematics teachers to endorse Flipped Classroom as their support instruction materials (SIM). Also, the findings will be presented to other school research coordinators during the District In-service Training for Teachers (INSET) to find action on their school's same issues as the researcher had. The researcher will also campaign to his colleagues to value research as the priority target in drafting their Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) of DepEd. The flipped videos such as Vlogs, Powerpoint

presentations aided with audio recordings, and other materials used in Flipped Classroom will be kept in school for future learners' or teachers' use. The flipped videos will be sent for review to the District LRDMDS coordinator and included in the Division LRDMDS portal to disseminate and utilize the content. Finally, the researcher wishes to publish the study findings in local scholarly journals and international research paper conferences.

REFERENCES

- Abah, J. A. (2020). An Appeal in the Case involving Conventional Teaching: Emphasizing the Transformation to Enhanced Conventional Teaching in Mathematics Education. *VillageMath Educational Review (VER)*, 1(1), 1-10.
<https://villagemath.net/journals/ver/v1i1/abah>
- Abulencia, A. (2019). Lived experience of principals in the implementation of K to 12 program in the Philippines. *EDUCARE: International Journal for Educational Studies*, 12(1), 1-24.
<https://journals.mindamas.com/index.php/educare/article/view/1243>
- Akram, M. J. (2010). Factors affecting the performance of teachers at higher secondary level in Punjab. *Pakistan Research Repository (PPR). Higher Education Commission, Islamabad*.
<http://pr.hec.gov.pk/jspui/bitstream/123456789/972/1/688S.pdf>
- Al-Marouf, R. S., Salloum, S. A., Hassanien, A. E., & Shaalan, K. (2020). Fear from COVID-19 and technology adoption: the impact of google meet during the coronavirus pandemic. *Interactives Learning Environments*, 1(16).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amsu.2021.01.051>
- Allahawiah, S., & Alsaraireh, M. (2014). The benefits of knowledge management and e-government in raising citizen engagement - Jordan case study. *Economics, Management and Financial Markets*, 9(1), 213-220.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330194104_THE_BENEFITS_OF_KNOWLEDGE_MANAGEMENT_AND_E-GOVERNMENT_IN_RAISING_CITIZEN_ENGAGEMENT-JORDAN_CASE_STUDY
- Avery, K., & Huggan, C. (2018). The flipped classroom: high school student engagement through 21st century learning. *IN EDUCATION*, 24(1), 4-21.
<https://doi.org/10.37119/ojs2018.v24i1.348>
- Bradley, K. (2016, July 18). How does shortening the school day affect students? *Tempesta Media*.
<https://showcase.tempestaedia.com/how-does-shortening-the-school-day-affect-students-aid-21622/>
- Cassibba, R., Ferrarello, D., Mammana, M.F., Musso, P., Pennisi, M., & Taranto, E. (2021). Teaching Mathematics at Distance: A Challenge for Universities. *Education Sciences*, 11(1), 1-20.
<https://dx.doi.org/10.3390/educsci11010001>
- Chanoknath, S., & Louangrath, P.I. (2015). Descriptive and inferential statistics. *International Journal of Research & Methodology in Social Science*, 1(1), 22-35. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1320727>
- Coronacion, A.P., & Roman, A.G. (2019). Enhancement teaching (ET), monitorial peer tutoring (MPT), and switch-to-teach (STT) intervention program for least learned competencies in mathematics. *International Journal of Science & Technology Research*, 8(12)3850-3854.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338147114>
- da Silva, B.G., Borges, Y.M., & Galo, R. (2020). The use of ludic resources for the teaching of probability and statistics in middle school. *Research Society and Development*, 9(11), 1-18.
<https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v9i11.10672>
- Das, D. (2019). Role of ICT for better mathematics teaching. *Shanlax International Journal for Education*, 7(4), 19-28.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1245150.pdf>
- Department of Education (1998). DO. 35, s. 1988. Utilization of Instructional Materials and Accountability Therefore.
<https://www.deped.gov.ph/1988/05/06/do-35-s-1988-utilization-of-instructional-materials-and-accountability-therefor/>
- Department of Education (2005). DO. 9, s. 2005 – Instituting Measures to Increase Engaged Time-On-Task and Ensuring Compliance Therewithin.
<https://www.deped.gov.ph/2005/03/02/do-9-s-2005-instituting-measures-to-increase-engaged-time-on-task-and-ensuring-compliance-therewith/>
- Department of Education (2009). DO. 109, s. 2009. Make-up Classes for Loss Schooldays.
https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2009/10/DO_s2009_109.pdf
- Department of Education (2012). DO. 31, s. 2012. Policy guidelines on the implementation of grades 1 to 10 of the K to 12 basic education curriculum (BEC) effective school year 2012-2013.
<https://www.deped.gov.ph/2012/04/17/do-31-s-2012-policy-guidelines-on-the-implementation-of-grades-1-to-10-of-the-k-to-12-basic-education-curriculum-bec-effective-school-year-2012-2013/>

- Department of Education (2016). K to 12 Curriculum Guide Mathematics (Grade 1 to Grade 10). https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Math-CG_with-tagged-math-equipment.pdf
- Department of Education (2016). DO. 35, s. 2016. The Learning Action Cell as a K to 12 Basic Education Program School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning. Retrieved from: https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/DO_s2016_035.pdf
- Fernandez-Martin, F.D., Romero-Rodriguez, J.M., Gomez-Garcia, G., & Navas-Parejo, M.R. (2020). Impact of the flipped classroom method in the mathematical area: a systematic review. *E Mathematics*, 8(0), 1-11. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7390/8/12/2162/pdf>
- Ferrer, I.M. (2017). Competency level of grade 10 mathematics teachers in Pangasinan, Philippines. *PSU JEMSS*, 1(1), 12-15. <http://psurj.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/2017-JEMS-03.pdf>
- Fidalgo, P., Thormann, J., Kulyk, O., & Lencastre, J. A. (2020). Students' perceptions on distance education: a multinational study. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 17(18), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-020-00194-2>
- Flipped Learning Network. (2014, April 4) The four pillars of F-L-I-P. https://flippedlearning.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/FLIP_handout_FNL_Web.pdf
- Fraser, J., Fahlman, D., Arscott, F., & Guillot, I. (2018). Pilot testing in a study of student retention and attrition in online undergraduate programs. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 19(1), 260-278. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1174051.pdf>
- Garza, S. (2014). The flipped classroom teaching model and its use for information literacy interaction. *Communications and Information Literacy*, 8(1), 7 – 22. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1089137.pdf>
- Gonzales, V. D. (2017). Cultural and economic benefits of festivals to community residents of Batangas, Philippines. *Asia Pacific of Education, Arts and Science*, 4(2), 14-22. <https://research.lpubatangas.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/APJEAS-2017.4.2.02.pdf>
- Gutierrez, K. (2014). 3 Key concepts that will help you understand learning in the digital age. *eLearning trends/eLearning*. <https://www.shiftelearning.com/blog/bid/349245/3-Key-Concepts-That-Will-Help-You-Understand-Learning-in-the-Digital-Age>
- Haramain, J.G.T. (2019). Undesirable factors affecting the performance level of public secondary school teachers in northern Luzon, Philippines. *International Journal of Research ad Review*, 6(2), 219-230. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335291357>
- Hase, S., & Kenyon, C., (2000). *From andragogy to heutagogy*, Ultibase, <http://ultibase.rmit.edu.au/Articles/dec00/hase2.htm>.
- Hernando-Malipot, M. (2019, June 25). Teachers' group laments lack of textbook for K to 12. *Manila Bulletin*, p 9. <https://www.pressreader.com/philippines/manila-bulletin/20190625/281792810561020>
- Into, C.A.D., & Gempes, G. P. (2018). Untold stories of teachers with multiple ancillary functions: a phenomenology of fortitude. *Journal of Advances in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(1), 13-25. https://www.tafpublications.com/gip_content/paper/Jahss-4.1.2.pdf
- Joshi, D. R. (2017). Influence of ICT in mathematics teaching. *International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field*, 3(1), 7-11. <https://www.academia.edu/33736648>
- K to 12 Mathematics Curriculum Guide (2016). K to 12 Curriculum Guide Mathematics (Grade 1 to Grade 10). https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Math-CG_with-tagged-math-equipment.pdf
- Katsa, M., Sergis, S., & Sampson, D. (2016). Investigating the potential of the flipped classroom model in K-12 mathematics teaching and learning. *13th International Conference on Cognition and Exploratory Learning in Digital Age*, 210 – 218. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED571429.pdf>
- Kuhfeld, M., Soland, J., Tarawasa, B., Johnson, A., Ruzek, E., & Liu, J. (2020). Projecting the potential impact of COVID-19 school closure on academic achievement. *Educational Research*, 49(8), 549-565. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.3102/0013189X20965918>
- Kunwar, R. (2020). Mathematics phobia: symptoms and ways to overcome. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, 8(8), 818-822. <http://www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2008103.pdf>

- Lo, C. K., & Hew, K. F. (2017). A critical review of flipped classroom challenges in K-12 education: possible solutions and recommendations for future research. *Research and Practice in Technology Enhanced Learning*, 12(4), 1-22.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s41039-016-0044-2>
- Mayer, R. (2014). Cognitive theory of multimedia learning. *The Cambridge Handbook of Multimedia Learning*. Cambridge University Press, 43-71.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139547369.005>
- Mullis, I.V.S., Martin, M.O., Goh, S., & Cotter, K. (Eds.) (2016). TIMSS 2015 encyclopedia: policy and curriculum in mathematics and science. <http://timssandpirls.bc.edu/timss2015/encyclopedia/countries/hong-kong-sar/the-mathematics-curriculum-in-primary-and-lower-secondary-grades/>
- Nachar, N. (2008). The Mann-Whitney U: a test for assessing whether two independent sample come from the same distribution. *Tutorials in Quantitative Methods for Psychology*, 4(1), 13-20. Retrieved from: <https://tqmp.org/RegularArticles/vol04-1/p013/p013.pdf>
- Orale, R.L., & Uy, M.E.A. (2018). When the spiral is broken: problem analysis in the implementation of spiral progression approach in teaching mathematics. *Journal of Academic Research*, 3(3), 14-24.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327232436>
- Perez, J.C., Bongcales, R.C.A., & Bellen, J.A. (2020). A scoping review on the implementation of the spiral progression approach. *Journal of Academic Research*, 1(1), 11-22.
<https://jar.ssu.edu.ph/index.php/JAR/article/view/198>
- Ramakrishnan, N., & Priya, J.J. (2016). Effectiveness of flipped classroom in mathematics teaching. *International Journal of Research-Granthaalayah*, 4(10), 57-62.
[https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v4.i10\(SE\).2016.2469](https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v4.i10(SE).2016.2469)
- Rashid, M., & Zaman, S. (2018). Effects of teacher's behavior on academic performance of students. *3rd International Conference on Research and Practices in Education, Islamabad, Pakistan*, 1-15.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325248514>
- Read, L., & Atinc, T. M. (2017). Investigation into using data to improve learning Philippine case study. *Global Economy and Development*. Brookings 1775 Massachusetts Avenue, NW Washington, DC.
<https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/global-20170307-philippines-case-study.pdf>
- Reingold, H., Danoff, C. J., & Pierce, C. (Eds) (2015). *The peeragogy handbook*. (3rd ed., 1-290). PubDomed and Pierce Press.
<https://peeragogy.org/Peeragogy.io-3/peeragogy-3-0-beta3.pdf>
- Rocha, A. V., & Mondelli, M. F. C. G. (2020). Applicability of the ear measurement for audiological intervention of tinnitus. *Brazilian Journal of Otorhinolaryngology*, 86(1), 14-22.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjorl.2018.07.010>
- Rosenbusch, K. (2020). Technology intervention: rethinking the role of education and faculty in the transformative digital environment. *Advances in Human Developing Resources*, 22(1), 87-101.
<https://doi.org/10.1177%2F1523422319886297>
- Saloviita, T., & Pakarinen, E. (2021). Teacher burnout explained: teacher-, students-, and organization-level variables. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 97(103221), 1-14.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103221>
- Sharma, R. (2019). Ensuring quality in teacher education. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 5(10), 21-24.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347827522>
- Siachifuwe, M. (2017). Teacher Based Factors Influencing Academic Performance among Learners in Open Learning Classes at Twin Palm Secondary School, Lusaka, Zambia. *International journal of humanities and social sciences*, 4, 96-101.
<https://doi.org/10.20431/2349-0381.0412012>
- Sintema, E. J. (2020). Effect of COVID-19 on the performance of grade 12 students: implications for STEM education. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology*, 16(7), 1-6.
<https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/7893>
- Smriti, A. (2018). Item analysis. *International Journal of Nursing Science Practice and Research*, 4(2), 6-7.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327906979>
- Somerville, R. L. (2013, May). *Reading motivation and achievement in 5th grade students* [Master's thesis, Goucher College, Maryland, United States of America]. Maryland Shared Open Access Repository.
https://mdsoar.org/bitstream/handle/11603/2364/ME_d_Somerville_actionres_Sp2013.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Sumuglu, U. (2021). A case study on teaching Turkish through distance education. *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*, 8(1), 174-190.
<https://doi.org/10.17220/ijpes.2021.8.1.278>

- Szparagowski, R. (2014). The effectiveness of the flipped classroom. *Honors Projects*, 127. <https://scholarworks.bgsu.edu/honorsprojects/127>
- Temelo, D.R.T., & Sillorequez, E.Y. (2013). Development of training design and materials to enhance grade 7 mathematics teachers' competencies. *WVSU Research Journal*, 2(2), 32-42. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=11857>
- Tuma, F. (2021). The use of educational technology for interactive teaching in lectures. *Annals of Medicine and Technology*, 62, 231-235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amsu.2021.01.051>
- Ulker, M., Gungor, H., & Cakiroglu, Y. (2021). The effect of conduction activities with native language and video learning on academic success in teaching. *Scientific Research Publishing*, 12(5), 1169-1185. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2021.125087>
- Ullah, O., & Iqbal, M. (2020). Comparison of Impact of Traditional and Modern Teaching Methods on Students' Performance at Elementary School Level. *Global Regional Review*, V(1), 386-395. doi:10.31703/grr.2020(V-I).42
- Wang, M. J. & Kang, J. (2006). *Cybergogy of engaged learning through information and communication technology: A framework for creating learner engagement*. In D. Hung & M. S. Khine (Eds.), *Engaged learning with emerging technologies* (pp. 225-253). New York: Springer Publishing.
- Wei, X., Cheng, I., Chen, N., ..., Zhai, X. (2020). Effect of the flipped classroom on the mathematics performance of middle school students. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09752-x>
- White, H., & Sabarwal, S. (2014). Quasi-experimental design and methods. *UNICEF Office of Research – Innocenti. Methodological Brief No. 8*, 1-13. https://www.unicef-irc.org/KM/IE/img/downloads/Quasi-Experimental_Design_and_Methods_ENG.pdf
- Yarkwah, C., & Agyei, E. (2020). Effects of sports participation on the academic performance of senior high school students in mathematics. *Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 8(2), 62-74. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339644899>
- Yilmaz, C., Bulus, H., Oguztuzun, S., Cihan, M., & Fidan, C. (2020). The activities of GST isozymes in stomach tissues of female obese patients. *Turk J Biochem*, 45(6), 883-889. <https://doi.org/10.1515/tjb-2020-0235>
- Yusuf, Y. Q., Mustafa, F., & Alqinda, M. (2017). The use of spelling bee game in teaching vocabulary to junior high school students. *Proceedings of The 1st National Conference on Teachers' Professional Development*, 242-251. <http://tpd.unsyiah.ac.id/publication/index.php/TPD/article/download/29/29>